

Bifunctional anatase TiO₂ thin films for electrochromic and room temperature gas sensing applications

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Abstract. TiO₂ thin films possessing multifunctional properties have application in broad range of spectrum such as dye sensitized solar cells, electrochromic windows, catalysis, gas sensors and lithium ion batteries. Chemical deposition techniques like spin coating; spray deposition and electrodeposition are receiving much attention because of their cost effective, ease in synthesis process. Among these techniques, spray deposition is suitable for large area deposition of transition metal oxide thin films. Anatase TiO₂ film is prepared by nebulized spray deposition technique using isopropanol as a solvent at a low substrate temperature of 200°C. The XRD and Raman studies indicated the formation of anatase TiO₂. Formation of homogeneously distributed pyramidal shaped nanograins was observed from the FESEM study. The electrochromic response of anatase TiO₂ film was studied by intercalating/deintercalating Li⁺ ions from 1 M LiClO₄ in propylene carbonate solution. TiO₂ films possess excellent electrochromic behavior with excellent coloration efficiency of 157 cm² C⁻¹, and a high reversibility of 92%. The TiO₂ thin films were further investigated for gas sensor applications. The TiO₂ thin films showed excellent response for ammonia gas detection as low as 5ppm at room temperature operating condition. The present report suggests that the nebulized spray deposited TiO₂ thin films can perform efficiently for electrochromic and gas sensing applications.

Keywords: TiO₂, Electrochromism, Gas sensor